

The Planck constant in quantised space

Sydney Ernest Grimm*

In philosophy of physics a model is actually a projection of the human awareness on the structure of reality. The model of quantised space is a geometrical construct so it questions the nature of the “picture” that emerges from the basic properties of the model.

Introduction

The problem with the concept of fields is that it is hard to imagine the structure of a phenomenon. Because we cannot observe the structure in a direct way. Fields like the universal electric field and the magnetic field are derived from the influence of these fields on observable phenomena. Actually the behaviour of an object under influence of a field.

In classic physics it was assumed that a field was the spatial extension of the properties of a phenomenon. That means without the phenomenon there is no field. But the general concept of modern quantum field theory is that phenomena emerge from an underlying field structure.^[1] This concept is confusing because the human imagination is not well equipped to handle an all-inclusive reality that emerges from non-observable spatial properties. So it is difficult to fully understand how our universe evolves if we are forced to quit our focus on the phenomena.

It is reasonable to construct reality with the help of those properties that can be categorised as universal properties. That means that at every position within the geometry of the universe these properties exist. Like the universal conservation laws, universal constants and universal principles. The model of quantised space^[2] is one of the constructs that is founded on the universal properties.^{[3][4]}

References:

1. Art Hobson (2013); "There are no particles, there are only fields". American journal of physics 81, 211.
DOI: 10.1119/1.4789885.
<https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/1204/1204.4616.pdf>
2. S.E. Grimm (2024); "The box without walls"
<https://zenodo.org/record/14540104>
3. S.E. Grimm (2020); "On the construction of the properties of discrete space"
<https://zenodo.org/records/3909268>

4. S.E. Grimm (2024); "On the geometrical structure of quantised space"
<https://zenodo.org/record/14556269>

* City of Amersfoort, the Netherlands
email: segrimm@proton.me
Orcid: 0000-0002-2882-420x

The boundary

A model isn't a construct of different "pictures" of the universe. It is the opposite. It is a blueprint of a reality that envelopes different pictures. Thus every picture fits into the blueprint. At least if the blueprint describes the whole picture. Like the model of quantised space pretends to be.

The trouble with this perspective are the boundaries. There cannot be a structure if reality has no internal boundaries. In the model of quantised space the boundary is the joint surface area of every unit because all the units together tessellate the volume of our universe. Unfortunately this idea questions the true nature of the boundaries too.

The argument that there must be a fixed volume with a boundary is determined with the help of recognition. Because we have noticed a rate of change (time) and the causal relation between time and the amount of changes of the phenomena around. Thus if we imagine that the structure of our universe is infinite small, the rate of change must be infinite high. And that is not what we observe.

The described basic properties of the units of quantised space – equal and invariant volume, deformable shape and an internal spherical shape forming mechanism – are projections of phenomenological reality on the underlying reality of quantised space. The description manifests geometry at the human scale size. It has the advantage that it is easier to imagine so it will simplify the communication about the model too. Unfortunately figure 1 shows that this approach has not only advantages.

The cross section in figure 1 shows the deformation of a joint surface area of 2 bodies with invariant volume. Simultaneously increasing the deformation of the 2 bodies results in the increase of surface area and visa versa.

figure 1

I can state that this is possible because volume becomes surface area and surface area becomes volume. Actually, I hypothesised a volume of infinite small “grains” and these grains can be part of the boundary of the unit or part of the volume of the unit. In other words, every change of the shape of a unit is actually the transfer of infinite small grains of volume within the unit.

Suppose I quit the geometry of phenomenological reality. Now what is left behind is the spherical shape forming mechanism. In other words, this mechanism is the unit of quantised space. The imaginary image in figure 2 shows the cross section of 2 such units with the shape of a cube. Both units have an undistorted part of the spherical shape forming mechanism and a distorted part. If every unit of quantised space have an identical spherical shape forming mechanism the “old” geometrical description still stands. Because the “power” of the spherical shape forming mechanism determines the volume, its surface area, etc.

figure 2

Without the concept of a tangible volume and related surface area there is still the existence of the spherical shape forming mechanism. Actually, the whole universe is made of it. What we recognise as different spatial properties – actually fields – is the distinction between a closed configuration (the undistorted part) and an open configuration (the distorted part). The first one is the universal scalar field (closed configuration) and the second one is the universal electric field (open configuration). But the spatial

properties don’t exist without the tessellation of the universe with units that manifest the spherical shape forming mechanism. In line with the previous conclusion that geometry is a model that originates from the observation of macroscopic phenomena (matter objects).

The open configuration of a unit acts like it is a composition of vectors in relation to the open configurations of the adjacent units. Because 2 opposite vectors are manifesting themselves at the position where both magnitudes are identical, creating the point of contact of an invisible boundary (see figure 2). The consequence is that the open configuration of the spherical shape forming mechanism cannot be compared with a “powerless” volume (no internal structure). Because if the latter is true, all the units of quantised space will have the same minimal surface area in relation to their volume (the rhombic dodecahedron, see figure 3).

figure 3

The total amount of surface area of a unit must be larger than the minimal surface area and the cause behind the difference is the lattice of the closed configurations (the universal scalar field). It forces all the open configurations to adapt to the asymmetry of the geometry of the scalars within the lattice (Kepler’s conjecture). I can visualise the surplus of surface area if I simulate the compression of solitary units till there is no empty space left (reference [4], page 2).

The quantum of energy

The idea that quantised space isn’t a construct of geometrical units with an internal spherical shape forming mechanism, questions the interpretation of the quantum of energy as a result of synchronisation. The problem is not if the change of open configurations of the distorted parts of the units is quantised, the problem is the question if the cause behind the quantification will have a more foundational origin. Because it is telling that the quantisation is directly related to the constant of length (ℓ_c).

figure 4

Planck's constant (h) originate from the interpretation of measured wave lengths of black body radiation – electromagnetic waves – at different temperatures (see figure 4). It is described in Planck's formula $E = h \nu$. In the Planck-Einstein relation the frequency (ν) is expressed in the covered distance under constant velocity of the electromagnetic wave (c) and the length of 1 wave (λ):

$$E = h \nu = h \frac{c}{\lambda} \rightarrow h \frac{c}{n \ell_c}$$

If I use the model of quantised space as the rest frame of our universe, it is reasonable to express the wave length (λ) with the help of (the multiple of) the constant of length ($n \ell_c$). Actually the size of 1 unit of quantised space.

figure 5

I can visualize the influence of 1 quantum of energy on the shape of a unit with the help of the diagram in figure 5. It shows the increase of the surface area of a unit with 1 quantum of energy and the corresponding increase of the magnitudes of the generated vectors within the magnetic field. The duration, expressed with the help of the constant

of length, is $t_q \approx 5,99 \times 10^{-23}$ Hz (period of time in figure 5). Thus $\ell_c = c \times t_q$. Anyway, the whole topological change in diagram 5 is perfectly smooth.

The synchronisation of the change of the internal spherical shape forming mechanism of every unit creates a type of fixed changes that we experience as time. I have termed the synchronised change the constant of quantum time (t_q) because the synchronisation is a manifestation of the universal electric field.

But if I replace my geometrical interpretation of the properties of quantised space with the concept of units that are compositions of spherical shape forming mechanism, I have to change my interpretation of the origin of Planck's constant. Because its origin isn't geometry, its origin is the spherical shape forming mechanism. Thus the amount of change is fixed because every unit has an identical spherical shape forming mechanism.

The waveform of the electromagnetic wave (figure 4) is the result of the push and push back of the involved units in relation to the shape of the units under influence of the spherical shape forming mechanism. So what is the Planck constant?

Conclusion

Planck's constant is the manifestation of the open configuration of the spherical shape forming mechanism of every unit of quantised space (known as the universal electric field). Its change is smooth (figure 5) and the velocity of the pass on of the change of energy is the constant speed of light (c). Thus the duration of the pass on over a distance that has the size of 1 unit (ℓ_c) will have a fixed duration (t_q). In other words, the amount of energy is limited (fixed) because of the constant speed of light (c) and the constant of length (ℓ_c). The measured quantisation of energy (h) of electromagnetic waves proves the existence of an underlying rest frame of units with the same spherical shape forming mechanism.